

Make Robots Be Bats: Specializing Robotic Swarms to the Bat Algorithm

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Abstract

Bat algorithm is a powerful bio-inspired swarm intelligence method with remarkable applications in several industrial and scientific domains. However, to the best of authors' knowledge, this algorithm has not been applied so far to the exciting field of swarm robotics. This paper describes the first physical and computational implementation of the bat algorithm to a swarm of simple robotic units. The swarm consists of a set of identical wheeled robots equipped with simple yet powerful components that replicate the most important features of the bat algorithm by either hardware or software. The swarm has been applied to the problem of coordinated exploration, where the individual self-organizing robots generate an intelligent collective behavior emerging from the interactions between the robots and with the environment. A computational and real-world experiment has been carried out to check the feasibility and performance of this approach. Our experimental results show that the bat algorithm is extremely well suited for this task, actually leading to surprisingly intelligent behavioral patterns much better than expected.

Keywords: swarm computation, swarm robotics, bat algorithm, coordinated exploration, behavioral patterns.

1. Introduction

1.1. Swarm Intelligence

For many years, the concept of *intelligence* was generally perceived to be an exclusive attribute of highly sophisticated individuals. Not surprisingly, this was also the

approach taken in the early days of the artificial intelligence field. However, nature provides several examples of groups of very simple individuals able to carry out complex tasks. Take, for instance, the colonies of social insects (ants, termites, bees, fireflies), and other animal formations (fish schooling, bird flocking, animal herding, and so on). They come up with astonishingly complex social behaviors from the combined efforts of individuals with extremely limited intelligence. Amazingly, this complex collective behavior emerges from a small set of simple behavioral rules exploiting only low-level interactions between individuals and with the environment (stigmergy) using decentralized control and self-organization.

In this context, one of the most exciting breakthroughs in artificial intelligence during the last decades is the adoption and subsequent popularization of this collective intelligence arising from a collection of simple, unsophisticated, and generally homogeneous agents collaborating together to solve a complex problem. This field, globally known as *swarm intelligence*, is overcoming the traditional mathematical approaches for solving optimization problems and laying the foundations for a new computational paradigm: the *swarm computation*. Under this new paradigm, there is no centralized intelligence controlling the swarm, taking decisions, and dictating how the swarm units should behave. Instead, *local* and (at some extent) *random* interactions between simple agents lead to the emergence of *global* sophisticated “intelligent” behaviors, unknown to the individual agents.

Nowadays, swarm intelligence is attracting increasing attention from researchers and practitioners owing to its potential applications to many problems. For instance, military and civil applications related to the control of unmanned vehicles have been described in [37, 38, 46]. Many other applications can also be found in the scientific literature; see [5, 12, 55] for several illustrative examples in different fields. The interested reader is also referred to [9, 20] for a comprehensive overview about the field of swarm intelligence, its history, main techniques, and applications.

1.2. Swarm Robotics

One of most relevant applications of swarm intelligence is robotics. Several scientific papers and research projects have shown that self-organizing swarm robots can potentially accomplish complex tasks and thus replace sophisticated and expensive robots by simple inexpensive drones, a research subfield usually referred to as *swarm robotics* [3, 10, 42, 48, 56]. As remarked by several authors [1, 6], swarm robotic systems offer several interesting advantages, such as:

- *Improved performance by parallelization:* swarm intelligence systems are very well suited for parallelization, because the swarm members can perform different actions at different locations simultaneously. This feature makes the swarm more flexible and efficient for complex tasks, as individual robots (or groups of them) can solve different parts of a complex task independently.
- *Task enablement:* groups of robots can do certain tasks that are impossible or very difficult for a single robot (e.g., collective transport of too heavy items, dynamic

target tracking, cooperative environment monitoring, autonomous surveillance of large areas).

- *Scalability*: inclusion of new robots into a swarm does not require reprogramming the whole swarm. Furthermore, because interactions between robots involve only neighboring individuals, the total number of interactions within the system does not increase dramatically by adding new units.
- *Distributed sensing and action*: a swarm of simple interconnected mobile robots deployed throughout a large search space possesses greater exploratory capacity and a wider range of sensing than a sophisticated robot. This makes the swarm much more effective in several tasks: exploration and navigation (e.g., in disaster rescue missions), nanorobotics-based manufacturing, microbotics for human body diagnosis, and many others.
- *Fault tolerance*: due to the decentralized and self-organized nature of the swarm, the failure of a single unit does not affect the completion of the given task.

All these advantages motivated a great interest in swarm robotics during the last two decades. The reader is kindly referred to Section 2 for further details on this issue.

1.3. Nature-Inspired Metaheuristic Methods

Most of swarm intelligence methods are computational metaphors based on the dynamics of natural groups. A classical example is the *ant colony optimization* (ACO) method, based on the behavior of colonies of ants, which are able to carry out difficult tasks unattainable for individual ants. Another example is the behavior of a flock of birds when moving all together following a common tendency in their displacements, an inspiration to the *particle swarm optimization* (PSO) method. Other examples include popular optimization methods such as artificial bee colony, firefly algorithm, cuckoo search, and bat algorithm. These and many other examples lead to a valuable set of computational intelligence techniques known as *nature-inspired metaheuristic methods*. The reader is referred to [49] for a gentle introduction to several recent nature-inspired metaheuristic methods; see also [54, 55].

Among them, the *bat algorithm* is an increasingly popular swarm intelligence algorithm originally proposed by Prof. Xin-She Yang in 2010 [50, 52]. The algorithm is based on the peculiar behavior of microbats (see Section 3 for details). In our experience, the bat algorithm has shown to be a very effective method to solve complex multimodal nonlinear continuous optimization problems involving a large number of variables [14, 15, 16, 17], including multiobjective problems [51]. Because of these reasons, this is the algorithm used in this paper.

1.4. Main Contributions and Structure of the Paper

Despite of its remarkable features, to the best of our knowledge, the bat algorithm has never been applied so far in the context of swarm robotics. Aimed at filling this gap, a previous paper in [41] presented some initial ideas about the application of the

bat algorithm to swarm robotics. However, that paper was based on very preliminary work and strongly affected by limitations of space. This paper is a substantial extension in several ways. The main contributions of this paper are:

1. First and utmost contribution of this work is *the first practical implementation of the bat algorithm for swarm robotics*. To the best of our knowledge, no previous application of the bat algorithm to swarm robotics has been reported so far in the literature.
2. Our implementation is performed at two levels: we introduce both *a physical robotic prototype* (described in Section 4.1) and *a computational robotic simulation framework* (described in Section 4.2).
3. A key differential factor of our approach is its *high specialization*. The general trend in swarm robotics is to create flexible drones able to support several algorithms with just minor (if any) modifications. Although this approach can be useful for comparative purposes among algorithms, it also yields biased comparisons since the design and components are not optimally chosen for each particular algorithm under analysis. Opposed to previous approaches in the field, our implementation has been carefully designed to replicate faithfully almost all features of the real bats and the bat algorithm (see Section 4.3 for details). In other words, all our (physical and logical) components are fully *optimized* to follow the bat algorithm principles as accurate as possible.
4. Our implementation has been applied to the problem of coordinated exploration of unknown static indoor environments. To this aim, three different computational scenes have been considered. The first one has been recreated from the real-world storage room where we perform our experiments with the real robotic swarm.
5. Our experiments show that the behavioral patterns observed in both the real and the simulated robotic swarms are very similar. Except for small deviations due to the typical noise in real-world conditions, the behavior and evolution of the robotic swarms at the physical and computational levels match each other fairly accurately.

This paper is organized as follows: previous work in the field of swarm robotics is briefly reported in Section 2. In Section 3 we provide the reader with a gentle overview about the bat algorithm and its main rules and features. We also describe the algorithm through its pseudocode. In Section 4 we describe the main features of our implementation of the bat algorithm for swarm robotics in terms of hardware and software. The analogies between our computational and physical swarm robotics implementation, the real bats, and the bat algorithm are also discussed in that section. The computational and real-world experiments about coordinated exploration with our robotic swarm are reported in detail in Section 5. The comparison of our approach with other alternative methods in the literature is addressed in Section 6. The paper closes with the main conclusions and some hints about our future work in the field.

2. Previous work

In this section, some previous work on swarm robotics is briefly reported. Our contribution spans both the physical and logical levels, so we organize our description on previous work accordingly, with Sections 2.1 and 2.2 devoted to the robotic platforms (physical level) and the robotic simulation frameworks (logical level), respectively.

2.1. Robotic Platforms

Swarm robotics has attracted much attention from the scientific community and the industry during the last decades. Pioneering research projects dating back the 80s and 90s (such as CEBOT, SWARMS or ACTRESS) made just preliminary advances, yet they set the foundations of the field. Since then, ambitious large-scale projects, such as the European-funded projects Swarm-bots (2001-2005), i-Swarm (2004-2008) and Swarmanoid (2006-2010) and initiatives from USA universities such as Harvard, MIT, Stanford, UPenn, ASU, Texas A&M and many others, have led to a boost in swarm robotics. As a result, several approaches have been described in the literature during the last few years.

One of the first approaches in the field was the robot *Khepera* [26], developed at the EPFL (Lausanne, Switzerland) in the mid 90s. It had 2 DC brushed servo motors with incremental encoders, 8 infrared proximity and ambient light sensors, for a total weight of 80 grams. It was sold to a thousand research labs worldwide, having served researchers for 10 years. Subsequently versions (such as *Khepera III* [29]) were released for the following decade along with some simulation platforms (see Section 2.2 for further details).

This work was later extended to a new robot, *Alice* [7, 8], developed by Gilles Caprari at the Autonomous Systems Lab at EPFL. From the very beginning, *Alice* designed to be autonomous, small (with just under 1 cubic inch, it featured a very amazingly small size for its time), and relatively inexpensive, making it affordable to construct and operate a large crowd of robots simultaneously (such as swarms of 90 robots working cooperatively, a very impressive number for that time). These micro-robots were even for sale at one time, not only for researchers but also for hobbyists. They were also highly configurable, with numerous extension modules (i.e., proximity infrared (IR) sensors, radio transmitter, IR communication module, gripper unit, camera extension, solar powered module, etc.) developed and applied to different research purposes.

A larger (CD size) robot was *Kobot* [43, 44]. Driven by two motors, eight IR sensors for obstacle avoidance, a digital compass for heading measurement, and a Zigbee wireless communication module with a range of 20 meters indoors, it was applied to analyze the self-organized flocking of a swarm of robots, such that a group of mobile robots should be able to wander in an environment by moving as a coherent group and avoiding obstacles as if they were a single “super-organism”.

The *e-Puck* was a popular cylindrical-shaped micro-robot designed to be robust and affordable enough to allow intensive classroom use [28]. It was equipped with eight IR proximity sensors, a color camera, two step motors, and 3D accelerometers; some other functional components could also be added. It was a popular robot for academic

purposes, particularly in small amounts. However, with a weight of about 200 grams, a diameter of 70 mm, a height of 50 mm, and a price of about 750-900 Euros, it was a little bit big and quite expensive for a large bulk, as required for crowds in swarm robotics.

Another popular micro-robot was *Jasmine*, a public open-hardware development to create a simple and cost-effective micro-robotics platform [19]. Equipped with two micro-controllers communicated through a high-speed two-wired TW1 interface, six communication channels and a geometry-perception channel based on separate IR transmitters and receivers and two DC motors with internal gears to allow movement forward and backward, this micro-robot has been widely used in swarm robotics studies, such as playing the role of a honeybee in aggregation scenarios [39]. A differential feature of *Jasmine* with respect to other swarms of robots is that *Jasmine* only supports local communication, while long distance communication is neither intended nor implemented, making it a good testbed for many problems. Other micro-robots well suited for swarm robotics are *S-bot* [27], *i-Swarm robot* [45], *SwarmBot* [21], *AMiR* (Autonomous Miniature Robot) [2], *Colias* [3] and its evolution, *Colias- Φ* [4].

Motivated by the recent trend of increasing the number of robots in the swarm, several relevant works are focusing on scalability issues and the challenges they present. Crowds of up to 100 robots (and even more) has been analyzed in projects, such as for the *I-swarm* and the *iRobot* swarm projects, by using *R-one*, *iRobot*, *SwarmBot* and other micro-robotics models [22, 23, 24, 36, 40]. A significant step in this regard was the small *kilobot*, by Michael Rubenstein, at the Self Organizing Systems Research Group at Harvard University [31]. It is a very small and cheap (about 15 USD each) micro-robot comprised of a microprocessor, sensors for visible and infrared light, and two tiny cell-phone vibration units that allow it to move across a table. Individually, kilobots are very simple; they can only perform three simple tasks: respond to light, measure a distance, and sense the presence of other robots. However, when combined, they can organize themselves into shapes, such as grouping into clusters based on their own color light (or that of their neighbors) or dispersing to fill a space. Kilobots are programmed all at once, as a group, using infrared light. Each kilobot gets the same set of instructions as the next. With just a few lines of programming, they can execute together complex natural processes, such as synchronize their flashing lights like a swarm of fireflies, or moving together towards a light source similar to the way bacteria search for food [32, 33]. Recently, a swarm of one thousand kilobots (actually 1024 robots, a real computer science “kilo”) has been reported in the literature [34]. With this huge amount, individual units are not really important; it does not even matter if one or a few robots break down, as the collective behavior of the swarm still prevails. In other words, a large robotic swarm provides a lot of flexibility and robustness, as the collective tendency of the swarm is highly immune to individual failures or breakages [35]. It also gives room to analyze some interesting configurations; for instance, a gradient formation, where a source robot generates a gradient value that is incremented as it propagates through the swarm, giving each robot a metrics of the distance value from the source, or for localization tasks, where robots determine their position in the coordinate system by communicating with already localized robots [33, 34, 35].

2.2. Robotic Simulation Frameworks

Swarm robotics is a very complex research area involving many different technologies including electronics, mechanics, physics, and computer hardware and software. In real-world experiments, it is almost impossible to make all these technologies work perfectly together. It requires a lot of investment in terms of material and human resources, time, and effort. Therefore, it is common in the field to rely on realistic simulations and fast prototyping by software to reduce the burden in developing a swarm of physical robotic units, make improvements on preliminary designs, and speed up the experiments by focusing on the most critical aspects without wasting time and resources in technical issues or environmental conditions. Because of these reasons, several robotic simulation frameworks for robots and robotic swarms have been developed, with different user interfaces and technical features. Some have been created exclusively for experimentation on particular robotic platforms and are not available for public use. Others are publicly available and very popular. In this section, we describe some of the most popular robot simulators suitable for robotic swarms. This description is by no means exhaustive, as many other robot simulators have been developed during the last few years. A detailed discussion on this topic is beyond the scope of this paper.

One of the first popular open source simulators for multi-robot simulation (including swarm robotics) is *Player/Stage/Gazebo* [11], a freeware open-source programming framework comprised of three main components:

- *Player*: a language-independent and platform-independent network server for robot control providing a clean and simple interface to the robot's sensors and actuators over the IP network. The client program can run on any machine provided that it has a network connection to the robot and source code is written in any language supporting TCP sockets.
- *Stage*: a multi-robot simulator of a population of mobile robots, sensors and actuators in a 2D bitmapped environment. Although it is a standalone application (so it can be used as a C++ library for robot simulation inside third-party programs), it is often used as a *Player* plugin module, providing populations of virtual devices for *Player*. Under that configuration, users can simply write robot controllers and sensor algorithms and scripts as clients of the *Player* server. This scheme has been successfully applied to 2D simulations of robots (see, for instance, [47]). *Stage* also provides a gallery of computationally cheap models lots of devices simulated without great fidelity for further simplicity. In this sense, it can be used as an environment for rapid prototyping of controllers for real robots provided that high fidelity to the real hardware is not really required.
- *Gazebo*: a multi-robot simulator for outdoor environments in 3D. Originally designed as a 3D alternative to *Stage* (in fact, controllers designed in each program are generally compatible with the other), *Gazebo* has evolved into a powerful robot simulator supporting 3D indoor and outdoor environments and providing access to multiple high performance physics engines (such as *ODE*, *Bullet*, *Simbody* and

DART) and using *OGRE* for high quality 3D graphics (including lighting, shadows and textures). It also includes modules and support for a variety of sensors and robot models.

Another popular multi-robot simulator is *Webots* [25]. It is a cross-platform commercial product to simulate a range of real robots through realistic models of many of the most popular commercial robots. The system provides a number of features such as realistic physics simulation in 3D graphical environments, customizable collision detection, unlimited number of robots, large compatibility with third-party software (such as *Matlab*), a library of accurate sensors models, and many others.

SwarmBot3D is a simulation tool for the S-bot robot of the *Swarmbot* project [24, 27]. It was developed on top of *Vortex*, a commercial physics simulation engine, and describes both robots and worlds as XML text files. It includes all hardware functionalities (sensors and mechanics) of a real S-bot. Each S-bot is created as a hierarchical combination of four mechanical sub-systems (treels, turret, front gripper arm and side gripper arm, the last ones being optional) at four levels of detail (fast, simple, medium, and detailed). It is possible to switch from one level to another on the fly during simulation for better performance. It also supports the handling a group of robots either as independent units or in a swarm configuration, as physical connections between robots can be created or removed dynamically during runtime.

Another popular robot simulation program is *Microsoft Robotics Developer Studio* (Microsoft RDS for short), a Windows-based framework in C# for control and simulation of robotic units [18]. It includes a programming editor for *Microsoft Visual Programming Language* (MVPL), a visual programming language developed specifically for RDS, and support for other packages with additional services (such as Soccer Simulation, Sumo Competition, Maze Simulator), and for simulation of the Kinect sensors, among others.

Some of the most popular robotic platforms described in previous section are also equipped with powerful simulation frameworks. For instance, several robot simulator programs have been developed for Khepera III and subsequent versions of this popular robot. Those programs include the *Khepera-Lisp Interface* (KHLI), *Khepera Simulator*, *YAKS*, *KiKS* (a *Khepera* simulator for *Matlab*), and the *Khepera III Toolbox* (a software toolbox for the *Khepera III* robot). Another example is *Jasmine*, from the University of Stuttgart, for which they developed a simulation system based on *Breve* (an open-source 3D simulation environment with an OpenGL display engine), with an object-oriented programming language called Steve and sensor models for Jasmine III robot, and two robot simulators developed at EPFL for the popular *e-puck* robotic platform: the *ENKI* system, an open source 2D physics-based robot simulator in C++, and *V-REP*, a 3D robot simulator based on a distributed control architecture. Other notable examples include *Mona*, an open-source open-hardware platform developed at the University of Manchester, the *R-one* robotic initiative from Rice University providing an operating system and accompanying software to program the *R-one* robotic platform, a widely used robotic kit for educational and research purposes, and *Kilobot* from Harvard University, and the recently released software code of the University of

Colorado Boulder crowdfunding *Droplets* project including a publicly accessible robot simulator.

3. The Bat Algorithm

The *bat algorithm* is a bio-inspired swarm intelligence algorithm originally proposed by Xin-She Yang in 2010 to solve optimization problems [50, 52]. The algorithm is based on the echolocation behavior of bats. The author focused particularly on microbats, as they use a type of sonar called *echolocation*, with varying pulse rates of emission and loudness, to detect prey, avoid obstacles, and locate their roosting crevices in the dark. In this paper we also adhere to this approach, so the term bats should be understood to refer to microbats henceforth. The interested reader is referred to the general paper in [53] for a comprehensive, updated review of the bat algorithm, its variants and applications.

3.1. Basic rules

The idealization of the echolocation of microbats can be summarized as follows (see [50] for details):

1. Bats use echolocation to sense distance and distinguish between food, prey and background barriers.
2. Each virtual bat flies randomly with a velocity \mathbf{v}_i at position (solution) \mathbf{x}_i with a fixed frequency f_{min} , varying wavelength λ and loudness A_0 to search for prey. As it searches and finds its prey, it changes wavelength (or frequency) of their emitted pulses and adjust the rate of pulse emission r , depending on the proximity of the target.
3. It is assumed that the loudness will vary from an (initially large and positive) value A_0 to a minimum constant value A_{min} .

In order to apply the bat algorithm for optimization problems more efficiently, some additional assumptions are strongly advisable. In general, we assume that the frequency f evolves on a bounded interval $[f_{min}, f_{max}]$. This means that the wavelength λ is also bounded, because f and λ are related to each other by the fact that the product $\lambda \cdot f$ is constant. For practical reasons, it is also convenient that the largest wavelength is chosen such that it is comparable to the size of the domain of interest (the search space, for optimization problems). For simplicity, we can assume that $f_{min} = 0$, so $f \in [0, f_{max}]$. The rate of pulse can simply be in the range $r \in [0, 1]$, where 0 means no pulses at all, and 1 means the maximum rate of pulse emission. With these idealized rules indicated above, the basic pseudo-code of the bat algorithm is shown in Algorithm 1. It is described in next paragraphs.

3.2. The algorithm

Basically, the algorithm considers an initial population of \mathcal{P} individuals (bats). Each bat, representing a potential solution of the optimization problem, has a location \mathbf{x}_i and velocity \mathbf{v}_i . The algorithm initializes these variables (lines 1-2) with random

Require: (Initial Parameters)

Population size: \mathcal{P}

Maximum number of generations: \mathcal{G}_{max}

Loudness: \mathcal{A}

Pulse rate: r

Maximum frequency: f_{max}

Dimension of the problem: d

Objective function: $\phi(\mathbf{x})$, with $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_d)^T$

Random number: $\theta \in U(0, 1)$

```
1:  $g \leftarrow 0$ 
2: Initialize the bat population  $\mathbf{x}_i$  and  $\mathbf{v}_i$ , ( $i = 1, \dots, n$ )
3: Define pulse frequency  $f_i$  at  $\mathbf{x}_i$ 
4: Initialize pulse rates  $r_i$  and loudness  $\mathcal{A}_i$ 
5: while  $g < \mathcal{G}_{max}$  do
6:   for  $i = 1$  to  $\mathcal{P}$  do
7:     Generate new solutions by adjusting frequency,
8:     and updating velocities and locations //eqns. (1)-(3)
9:     if  $\theta > r_i$  then
10:        $\mathbf{s}^{best} \leftarrow \mathbf{s}^g$  //select the best current solution
11:        $\mathbf{ls}^{best} \leftarrow \mathbf{ls}^g$  //generate a local solution around  $\mathbf{s}^{best}$ 
12:     end if
13:     Generate a new solution by local random walk
14:     if  $\theta < \mathcal{A}_i$  and  $\phi(\mathbf{x}_i) < \phi(\mathbf{x}^*)$  then
15:       Accept new solutions
16:       Increase  $r_i$  and decrease  $\mathcal{A}_i$ 
17:     end if
18:   end for
19:    $g \leftarrow g + 1$ 
20: end while
21: Rank the bats and find current best  $\mathbf{x}^*$ 
22: return  $\mathbf{x}^*$ 
```

Algorithm 1: Bat algorithm pseudocode

values within the search space. Then, the pulse frequency, pulse rate, and loudness are computed for each individual bat (lines 3-4). Then, the swarm evolves in a discrete way over generations (line 5), like time instances (line 19) until the maximum number of generations, \mathcal{G}_{max} , is reached (line 20). For each generation g and each bat (line 6), new frequency, location and velocity are computed (lines 7-8) according to the following

evolution equations:

$$f_i^g = f_{min}^g + \beta(f_{max}^g - f_{min}^g) \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_i^g = \mathbf{v}_i^{g-1} + [\mathbf{x}_i^{g-1} - \mathbf{x}^*] f_i^g \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_i^g = \mathbf{x}_i^{g-1} + \mathbf{v}_i^g \quad (3)$$

where $\beta \in [0, 1]$ follows the random uniform distribution, and \mathbf{x}^* represents the current global best location (solution), which is obtained through evaluation of the objective function at all bats and ranking of their fitness values. The superscript $(.)^g$ is used to denote the current generation g .

The best current solution and a local solution around it are probabilistically selected according to some given criteria (lines 8-11). Then, search is intensified by a local random walk (line 12). For this local search, once a solution is selected among the current best solutions, it is perturbed locally through a random walk of the form:

$$\mathbf{x}_{new} = \mathbf{x}_{old} + \epsilon \mathcal{A}^g \quad (4)$$

where ϵ is a random number with uniform distribution on the interval $[-1, 1]$ and $\mathcal{A}^g = \langle \mathcal{A}_i^g \rangle$, is the average loudness of all the bats at generation g .

If the new solution achieved is better than the previous best one, it is probabilistically accepted depending on the value of the loudness. In that case, the algorithm increases the pulse rate and decreases the loudness (lines 13-16). This process is repeated for the given number of generations. In general, the loudness decreases once a bat finds its prey (in our analogy, once a new best solution is found), while the rate of pulse emission decreases. For simplicity, the following values are commonly used: $\mathcal{A}_0 = 1$ and $\mathcal{A}_{min} = 0$, assuming that this latter value means that a bat has found the prey and temporarily stop emitting any sound. The evolution rules for loudness and pulse rate are as follows:

$$\mathcal{A}_i^{g+1} = \alpha \mathcal{A}_i^g \quad (5)$$

$$r_i^{g+1} = r_i^0 [1 - \exp(-\gamma g)] \quad (6)$$

where α and γ are constants. Note that for any $0 < \alpha < 1$ and any $\gamma > 0$ we have:

$$\mathcal{A}_i^g \rightarrow 0, \quad r_i^g \rightarrow r_i^0, \quad \text{as } g \rightarrow \infty \quad (7)$$

In general, each bat should have different values for loudness and pulse emission rate, which can be computationally achieved by randomization. To this aim, we can take an initial loudness $\mathcal{A}_i^0 \in (0, 2)$ while the initial emission rate r_i^0 can be any value in the interval $[0, 1]$. Loudness and emission rates will be updated only if the new solutions are improved, an indication that the bats are moving towards the optimal solution. As a result, the bat algorithm applies a parameter tuning technique to control the dynamic behavior of a swarm of bats. Similarly, the balance between exploration and exploitation can be controlled by tuning algorithm-dependent parameters.

Figure 1: Identical wheeled robots used for our implementation of the bat algorithm and main components: a single-board microcontroller *Arduino UNO* (for programming and connectivity), ultrasonic sensors (for collision avoidance), magnetometer (for spatial orientation), and bluetooth card (for wireless data exchange and communication).

4. Bat Algorithm Implementation for Swarm Robotics

In this section we report our implementation of the bat algorithm described above to swarm robotics by using a swarm of simple robotic units. This implementation is performed at two levels: the robotic platform (physical level) and the robotic simulation framework (computational level). They are described in Sections 4.1 and 4.2, respectively.

4.1. Robotic Platform for Bat Algorithm

Our robotic swarm for bat algorithm consists of a set of identical wheeled robots. Figure 1 shows two robots of the swarm along with some of their most distinctive

components. Each robot is equipped with a kit of simple yet powerful hardware components that replicate the most relevant features of the bat algorithm, while some other features are replicated by software. The hardware and software implementation of the robotic platform are described in Sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2, respectively.

4.1.1. Hardware implementation

The robot is mounted on a rigid chassis, shown in green in Figure 1. The chassis and other mechanical parts (such as the wheels and holders) have been generated by 3D printing from a 1.75 mm PLA (polylactic acid) filament by using a fully enclosed domestic desktop FFF Witbox 3D printer by Spanish manufacturer QB. The robot moves through two side wheels driven by two continuous rotation servo motors. The chassis also hosts the battery holders with their board connectors (cables terminated with a standard 5.5×2.1mm, center positive barrel jack connector) and the electronics of our robotic unit. The main electronic components are:

1. a *single-board microcontroller*: in our implementation we use the popular microcontroller *Freaduino UNO*, an *Arduino*-compatible board based on *Arduino Uno Rev3* design and manufactured by *ElecFreaks*. The board comes with a single-chip microcontroller *ATmega 328* by *Atmel*, a 8-bit RISC-based microcontroller at a clock speed of 16MHz, with 32kB IPS flash memory, 2kB SRAM, 1kB EEPROM, 14 digital I/O pins (of which 6 provide PWM output) and 6 analog pins. The device operates between 3.3V and 5V. *Freaduino UNO* has been chosen because it provides a very good combination of small size, affordable price, and reasonable computing power. It is not only fully compatible with *Arduino Uno Rev3* (including all shields, programs and IDE), but also cheaper and easier to use. It also comes with some small improvements on the hardware (for instance, a 3.3V/5V switch that allows to connect 3.3V modules such as XBee directly to the board, a DC/DC switch mode power supply on the PCB to support connection with more LEDs, motors and other demanding peripherals, more visible location of LED indicators, and a wider range of external input, 7~23V DC). The single-board micro-controller is responsible for all programming tasks and the connectivity among the different components of the robot. We also added a protoshield and a mini breadboard for further connectivity of electronic components. The protoshield is plugged on top of the board microcontroller to gain access to all microcontroller pins plus a row of five +5V and GND pins each for easy access. The mini solderless breadboard, shown in white in Fig. 1(bottom, left and right), can be used for tasks such as temporary circuits (e.g., removable sensors) and fast prototyping.
2. an *ultrasound sensor*: in this work, we use the ultrasound sensor *HC-SR04*, also manufactured by *ElecFreaks*. It is an ultrasonic sensor operating at 5V DC that uses sonar to compute the distance to an object, much like bats or dolphins actually do. Each *HC-SR04* module includes an ultrasonic transmitter, a receiver and a control circuit, with 4 pins for power, trigger (transmitter), echo (receiver), and ground. Some other technical features will be discussed in detail in Section 4.3. The ultrasound sensor is used for collision avoidance with static and dynamic

objects (including other robots in the swarm) as well as with the physical 3D environment.

3. a *magnetometer*: in this work, we use the triple-axis magnetometer board *HMC-5883L*. This user-friendly compass is a 3.3V max chip with added circuitry to make it 5V-safe logic and power, so that it can be connected to either 3 or 5V microcontrollers. It uses I2C serial bus for easy interface to communicate. Its internal functioning is based on the anisotropic magnetoresistive (AMR) technology by *Honeywell*, with AMR directional sensors having a full range of ± 8 gauss and a resolution of up to 2 milligauss. The magnetometer is used in this work for global spatial orientation of the robotic units of the swarm regardless their physical environment.
4. a *Bluetooth card*: we use the *HC-05* Bluetooth sub-module, which uses short-wavelength UHF radio waves for wireless communication. *HC-05* can be set to be master or slave and runs at 3.3V but also supporting operation at 5V power and interface to our microcontroller at 5V signal level with level shifting. We use it for wireless communication and data exchange over short distances (about a range of 10 meters) among the robots of the swarm and with a central server for tracking purposes.

All these components are connected to different I/O pins in a rather standard way. The detailed description of these connections is out of the scope of this paper and will be omitted here to keep the paper to a manageable size.

4.1.2. Software implementation

The robotic platform described in previous section was programmed by using several software libraries and tools. All our source code was implemented on a personal computer through the open-source *Arduino IDE*. Then, it was compiled with *AVR-GCC*, a compiler for *Atmel* AVR microcontrollers. The software library *AVR Libc* was also used for compilation. Other external libraries and files have been used for different tasks; for instance, *Servo.h* was used for controlling the servomotors for robot motion; *I2C.h*, *Wire.h*, *Serial.h* and others have been used for communication via Bluetooth and with I2C devices (e.g., the magnetometer). The resulting binary code (in HEX format) from compilation is transferred to the microcontroller through a RS232 serial port to TTL converter for final loading and execution.

4.2. Robotic Simulation Framework for Bat Algorithm

The bat algorithm-based robotic swarm has also been simulated graphically by using a framework specifically developed by the authors for this work. The framework has been created in *Unity 5*, a popular multiplatform game engine especially praised by its portability, supporting all personal computer operating systems and video game consoles as well as most of mobile devices and websites. This game engine comes with many different features and tools for the accurate simulation of 3D scenes, including high-quality graphics (e.g., lighting, shadows, textures, and materials) for advanced photo-realistic rendering, a powerful physics engine with realistic rigid/soft body simulations and forward/inverse kinematics, powerful navigation tools, advanced algorithms

Figure 2: Computational tools used for the robotic simulation framework: (top) graphical editor of game engine *Unity 5*; (bottom) programming framework for *JavaScript* in *Visual Studio*.

for collision detection, and so on. It also provides a nice graphical editor, shown in Fig. 2(top), with different windows and workspaces for the project, scene view, game view, hierarchy, toolbars, inspector, and many other features.

Unity 5 supports the programming languages *C#* and *JavaScript*. All programming code for our robotic simulation framework has been created in *JavaScript* using the *Visual Studio* integrated programming environment (IDE). A screenshot of the *Visual Studio* editor with part of our code for the bat algorithm in *JavaScript* is shown in Fig. 2(bottom). This source code can be further compiled to generate standalone applications that can be executed autonomously under different hardware configurations and operating systems. An example is shown in Figure 3, where the main window of the

Figure 3: Standalone application from our bat-algorithm-based robotic simulation framework for swarm robotics. Main window of Mac OS X version is displayed.

application for Mac OS X system is depicted¹. It contains three buttons to access three different pre-computed 3D scenes and a fourth button to exit the application. The 3D scenes, labelled as Level 1 to Level 3 in increasing order of geometric complexity, are displayed in Figure 4 (top to bottom). They correspond to different configurations of a closed storage room with several cardboard boxes stacked in a very messy way (even occasionally forming structures such as tunnels and passageways the robots can take advantage of). In all cases, the target point used in our experiments in Section 5 is displayed as two concentric circles in red. Further details about these scenes and their use for coordinated exploration can be found in Section 5.

4.3. Analogies of Our Implementation with the Real Bats and the Bat Algorithm

As mentioned, all physical components of our implementation of a robotic swarm have been carefully chosen to replicate the most relevant features of the real bats and the bat algorithm by either hardware or software. This section discusses the analogies and differences found in the process. Our discussion is briefly summarized in Table 1, where we compare the real microbats, the bat algorithm, and our implementation (arranged in columns) for different features (arranged in rows). For each feature, the

¹This application was on show last February during the ICHSA 2017 conference. It was installed in a laptop publicly available to conference attendees for live execution. At that time, we received very positive comments and valuable feedback from several conference delegates.

Figure 4: Graphical representation of the three 3D scenes (labelled as Level 1 to Level 3 from top to bottom, respectively) available from main window of the application displayed in Figure 3.

	<i>Real microbats</i>	<i>Bat algorithm</i>	<i>Our approach</i>
<i>No centralized behavior:</i>	✓	✓	✓
<i>No vision abilities:</i>	✓	N.A.	✓
<i>Ultrasound based:</i>	✓	✓	✓
<i>Operating frequency:</i>	25–150 kHz	✓	40 kHz
<i># cycles burst:</i>	10–20	N.A.	8
<i>Operating time:</i>	in milliseconds	N.A.	~60 milliseconds
<i>Accuracy range:</i>	mm~cm	N.A.	~3 mm
<i>Traveling range of pulses:</i>	meters	N.A.	0.02~5 meters
<i>Loudness tuning:</i>	✓	✓	✓
<i>Pulse rate tuning:</i>	✓	✓	✓
<i>Flying abilities:</i>	✓	N.A.	×

Table 1: Analogies and differences among the real microbats, the bat algorithm and our implementation for several features, arranged in rows (see the main text for full interpretation of the table).

symbol ✓ indicates that it is supported; otherwise, the symbol × is used. N.A. stands for *Not Applicable*, meaning that this particular feature does not apply for the analyzed approach.

The most important features replicated by hardware are:

1. *No centralized behavior:* Microbats in nature do neither have a leader of the group nor take centralized decisions. Instead, they synchronize their individual decisions for many important issues such as switching communal roosts, communal nursing, communal breeding, social thermoregulation (mutual warming), and so on. In fact, microbats are excellent examples of non-centralized, communal decision-making. This is also a fundamental ingredient of the bat algorithm. As any other swarm intelligence approach, there is not a centralized system controlling the swarm behavior, something similar to what actually happens in our implementation. There is a central server, but it does not control the system at all; it is used for tracking and monitoring purposes only, but it does not take any decision about how to move or whatever. All robotic units move and behave on an individual (yet coordinated) basis. In our case, the bat algorithm is encoded in the microcontroller board and executed locally. The robots communicate relevant information (such as location, velocity and frequency) to other swarm members but the dynamics of any robot is computed locally.
2. *No vision abilities:* Similar to some microbats, our robots are not provided with vision abilities at all; to this purpose, we refrain from including a camera or any other device for vision (including infrared sensors, thermal cameras, and the like). This is opposed to many usual approaches in swarm robotics, which tend to allow as many sensors as possible to make the robots more powerful and support a wider range of algorithms. In our philosophy, we should adhere to the principles

of bat algorithm, so this option is unacceptable.

3. *Ultrasound based:* To faithfully replicate real bats and the bat algorithm, our robots must rely on echolocation. This is what we do in our implementation. As described in Section 4.1.1, our ultrasound sensors are based on sonar technology for collision avoidance and interaction with other robots and the environment, much like the real bats do.
4. *Operating frequency:* Although the actual range can vary depending on the microbat specie (and there are about 930 recognized so far), their typical frequencies oscillate in the range 25-150 kHz. Each ultrasound pulse of our robots operates at a constant frequency of 40 kHz, well within the range of real bats. Furthermore, it is well-known that many microbats use constant-frequency signals for echolocation, which is similar to what our robots actually do. Other microbats can use short, frequency-modulated signals to sweep through about an octave. We are currently considering options to tune the ultrasound sensor by hardware so that it can behave approximately that way.
5. *# of cycles of burst:* Again, this value depends on the particular microbat specie (and also on environmental conditions), with the typical range about 10-20 cycles of burst. Our robots have small ultrasound sensors sending an 8 cycle burst of ultrasound pulses, very similar to the typical value of real bats.
6. *Operating time:* The robot captures its echo with signals lasting in the order of milliseconds, exactly as the real bats actually do. For our sensor, the manufacturer advises to consider over 60 ms measurement cycle, in order to prevent trigger signal to the echo signal.
7. *Accuracy range:* The accuracy range of the sensor is about 3 millimeters, very similar to that of some real bats.
8. *Traveling range of pulses:* in our robots this value is between 2–500 centimeters, similar to the range of a few meters of several bats.

Other interesting bat algorithm features are difficult to replicate by hardware, so they have been replicated by software to ensure the highest fidelity of our robotic swarm to the bats and the original bat algorithm. These features include:

1. *Loudness tuning:* The loudness can be modulated in the source programming code. This is not surprising, since our source code is actually an implementation of the bat algorithm.
2. *Pulse rate tuning:* The pulse rate of our ultrasound signals can be modified by software to adapt to different conditions, as it typically happens with bats in the real world and in good agreement with the bat algorithm.

Finally, there is an important feature of the real bats that we do not emulate in our approach: the ability to fly. While it is not really required (from a mathematical point of view) for the bat algorithm (although somehow assumed in the description of the method), this is a serious drawback towards the realism of our robotic units, especially regarding 3D environments, as they are the natural niche of microbats in real life. However, research in this area is still in its early infancy and this problem is clearly

beyond the scope of this paper; more details on this issue will be discussed in Section 6.

5. Computational and Real-World Experiments

5.1. Experimental Settings

As described above, the major goal of this paper is to design and implement a robotic swarm replicating the real bats and the bat algorithm as faithfully as possible. Once implemented, our robotic swarm is tested in some experiments about coordinated exploration, where the objective is to reach a target point in a static 3D indoor scene. It is assumed that the robots have neither knowledge about the location of such a target point nor about the possible paths leading to it. However, in order to define a proper fitness function for the experiments, each robot is provided with the numerical value of its distance to the target point at each iteration step. Still, the robot has no clue about the physical area around it or where to move (being thus impelled to explore the environment). Solving this problem is a difficult task for the robots. For instance, it might happen that the path in front of a mobile robot is blocked by an object in the environment (static obstacle), or by another moving robot of the swarm (dynamic obstacle). Since the robot cannot see the obstacle, it keeps moving forward until the ultrasound sensor detects it (at which point, different behavioral patterns can emerge; see Section 5.2). In this situation, the use of a robotic swarm becomes very advantageous, due to its wider exploratory capacity with respect to a single robot. Ideally, each robot of the swarm explores its surrounding area and communicates its position, velocity, and frequency to the other members of the swarm, improving the global efficiency of the whole swarm to find the target.

To verify this assertion, a series of experiments has been conducted at both computational and real-world levels. For the former, we carried out series of 100 computer executions for each of the three different scenes displayed in Fig. 3, where the initial locations of the robots are set randomly for each individual execution. Regarding the real-world level, we carried out just 20 simulations instead of 100 because of battery constraints, using the first scene. Unfortunately, the dimensions of the real room do not allow us to take wide range pictures, only close-up (mostly uninformative) photos. Due to this reason, we rely on computer simulations to show our results.

Since our robots do not fly, they can only move on the ground. While this is not a problem in our real-life experiments, it is important to determine the walkable areas of the scenes for the computational experiments. Our game engine is particularly useful in this regard: *Unity 5* provides powerful options to compute and handle such areas through a tool called *navigation mesh* (or *navmesh*), a collection of non-overlapping two-dimensional convex polygons defining areas of the map fully traversable by the robots. Figure 5 shows the navigation meshes (in green) associated with the three scenes (from top to bottom) in this paper. We show both the isometric view (left) and the top view (right) for full visualization of all scene features. Note that the different objects in the scene (mostly cardboard boxes piled up in a messy way) are surrounded by a security area (in vanilla color) defined by a threshold value of the normal distance

Figure 5: Navigation mesh (in green) representing the walkable areas for the three scenes (from top to bottom) in Figure 4: (left) isometric view; (right) top view.

from the object. This is used to prevent collisions between the objects and the moving robots. In real-life experiments, it corresponds to a threshold value for the ultrasound sensor, which can be set as low as 2cm and as high as 400cm.

Figure 6: Computational and real-world experiment about coordinated exploration for swarm robotics: general view (top-left), top view (bottom-right) and selected regions of interest (bottom-left & middle).

5.2. Our Results

First and most important observation of our experiments is that *the behavior of the robotic swarm is amazingly similar for both the computer and real-world experiments*, provided that we use the same scene, number of robots, and initial locations. For illustration, Figures 6 and 7 shows a screenshot of one execution of the computer experiment for the first scene along with the pictures of its real-world counterpart. We selected this particular screenshot to show some interesting features for comparison between the computer and real-world simulations. Figures 6 and 7 share a similar structure: the upper part of the figure shows the computer simulation of the full scene with isometric view, while the image on the rightmost part shows the top view. Ten robots were deployed in the scene with initial random locations and they evolved according to the bat algorithm, as described above. They are displayed as light blue boxes on top of a moving basis (not visible for these views). A rectangle (in red and pink in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively) shows a selected region of interest (ROI) in both pictures. These regions are further enlarged (as indicated by arrows of similar colors) for better visualization. The ROIs contain some robotic units highlighted with dashed circles of different colors in the images for easier identification. We also show a picture of the same real-world experiment with the same robots for comparison.

Figure 7: Computational and real-world experiment about coordinated exploration for swarm robotics: general view (top-left), top view (bottom-right) and selected regions of interest (bottom-left & middle).

We remark that the computational and the real-world simulations are performed in a completely independent way, but for the same scene (the computer world is a replica of the real environment) and the same initial locations for the real and the simulated robots. We noticed a very similar behavior of the robotic swarm in both experiments. Their positions and motions match very well, as shown in those pictures.

Another important observation is that *the evolution of the robotic swarms in computer and real-world experiments* (albeit globally very similar) *is not really identical*. In our experiments, we noticed that the actual positions of the real and the simulated robots do not match exactly frame-by-frame during the simulation timeline, because of several factors. In some cases, the real-world robotic swarm is advanced or delayed with respect to the computer robotic swarm. In other cases, the evolution of the robots is not exactly the same, probably due to technical factors (such as the sensor sensitivity, a different position of an object in the computational and real-world scene, or others). Yet, the general dynamics of the swarm is surprisingly similar in most cases.

Our experimental results have been amazingly good, actually much better than expected. We found a number of interesting behavioral patterns to be further explored. For instance, in our prior opinion, the robots should get trapped in challenging con-

Figure 8: (top-bottom, left-right) Four screenshots of Video 1 showing some interesting behavioral patterns (see the main text for details). The pictures have been edited for arrows and numbering.

figurations such as U and V shapes (where the robotic units would be forced to come back), in cases of traffic jam owing to overcrowding, or in cases of narrow passages and corridors where only a single robot could advance at once. However, we found surprisingly intelligent behaviors where some units in a formation leave the group to explore other alternative ways, thus overcoming the previous bottleneck situations. Sometimes, the robots turn around without any apparent advantage for doing so; however, the reason becomes clear after some iterations, when we realized that the unit found a way to reach a better location than its robotic mates in the formation, even although it initially implies to move further away from better locations. This behavior is shown in Figure 8, where the trajectories of the robots are indicated by green arrows, except that in yellow for robot #1. This robot is initially moving towards the swarm (top-left), even skipping a promising path on its left in order to get closer to the swarm (top-right). However, there are several robots ahead blocking the way, so the robot (now at the rear of the queue) suddenly stops and changes its direction to take the path on the left that it previously overlooked (bottom-left). This strategy turns out to be successful, as it gets closer to the start of the queue (bottom-right). On the other hand, the decision to move towards the swarm overlooking other potential paths

Figure 9: (top-bottom, left-right) Four screenshots of Video 2 showing some interesting behavioral patterns (see the main text for details). The pictures have been edited for arrows.

seems to be related with the value of the distance from the robot to the current global best location of the swarm, according to Eq. (2). This is also shown for robot #2, which follows a similar behavior in the first two screenshots. See also *video 1* of the accompanying material for the full animation of these interesting behavioral patterns.

Figure 9 shows an interesting example of a bifurcation behavior. Initially, the swarm moves in formation searching for the target point (top-left) but it reaches a static obstacle along the way. Then, the formation splits up into two groups, moving in different directions: one is driven by the current global best, while the second one is driven by a swarm member at the middle of the formation but relatively close to the target. Once this robot starts moving in this new direction, it becomes the new global best (top-right). As such, it drags most the swarm; still, two robots (including the former global best) continue on the other way (bottom-left), initially moving farther from the target point (and worsening their fitness function as a result) but also circumventing the obstacle, until finally getting the target point as well (bottom-right). See *video 2* of the accompanying material for the full animation of this bifurcation behavior.

<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Meaning</i>	<i>Range of Values</i>	<i>Selected Value</i>
\mathcal{P}	population size	10 – 20	10
g	maximum number of generations	100 – 300	200
\mathcal{A}^0	initial loudness	(0, 2)	0.5
\mathcal{A}_{min}	minimum loudness	[0, 1]	0
r^0	initial pulse rate	[0, 1]	0.25
f_{max}	maximum frequency	[0, 10]	2
α	multiplicative factor	(0, 1)	0.5
γ	exponential factor	[0, 1]	0.4

Table 2: Bat algorithm parameters and their values in this paper.

5.3. Parameter Tuning

A critical issue when working with nature-inspired metaheuristic methods is the parameter tuning. It is well-known that the performance of these methods is strongly dependent on the choice of suitable values for their parameters. Moreover, such values are problem-dependent, making it hard to determine good values in advance. Therefore, although there are some papers describing suitable values for some problems, our choice must be necessarily empirical. To this purpose, we carried out numerous computer simulations for different parameter values. The different parameters used in this paper are arranged in rows in Table 2. For each parameter, the table shows (in columns) its symbol, meaning, range of values, and the parameter value chosen in this paper.

The most important parameters in the bat algorithm are:

- *population size*: in general, increasing the number of individuals decreases the number of required iterations, but it also increases the number of function evaluations. Therefore, a trade-off between both situations must be achieved for better performance. In this work, we tested populations ranging from 10 to 20 robots and found that increasing the number of individuals reduces the required time for convergence, but some of the interesting behaviors reported above were lost because of fast convergence (with 15–20 robots in a relatively small room, there is a large probability that at least one is randomly initialized very near to the target). Therefore, we finally decided to set this value to 10 robots for comparative purposes with the real-world experiments, as we have only 10 robots.
- *maximum number of iterations*: we tested our method for values of this parameter in the range 100 – 300 and found that the method converged in less than 200 iterations in all our executions, so we finally set this parameter to 200 iterations. To prevent wasting computation time, we also stop the execution when the swarm achieves convergence (i.e., all units of the swarm reach the target point).

- *initial and minimum loudness and parameter α* : they are set to 0.5, 0, and 0.5, respectively. However, from our computer experiments we noticed that our results do not change significantly for values of the initial loudness in the whole range $(0, 2)$, meaning that this parameter is very robust against variations on that interval. We used $\alpha = 0.5$ as suggested in some previous papers, but did not check other values for this parameter in detail.
- *initial pulse rate and parameter γ* : of these two parameters, the initial pulse rate is the most relevant. In fact, parameter γ only affects the very early iterations. We set their values to 0.25 and 0.4, respectively.

With this choice of parameter values, we run the bat algorithm iteratively. Positions and velocities of the robots are computed and ranked according to our fitness function explained above. The iterative process stops once either all robots of the swarm have arrived at the target point successfully or the maximum number of iterations is reached, whatever comes first.

5.4. Convergence Issues

An important issue of our approach is the convergence of the robotic swarm to the target point. To test this issue, we modified the spatial configuration of the three scenes in this paper in many different ways (adding new obstacles in the map, moving the location of some objects, removing objects, and so on) to get hundreds of variations of different geometric complexity.

To our surprise (and delight), after thousands of simulations, we did not find any configuration so far unsolvable for the robots, provided that at least one 2D solution exists. Our experiments show that the bat algorithm is very well suited for this task. It also shows that our implementation for robotic swarms performs extremely well, actually much better than we anticipated.

Of course, the convergence time of the process can vary a lot for each individual execution, depending on the geometry of the scene, initial location of the robots, population of the swarm, and other factors. Just for illustration, Figure 10 shows the convergence diagram for the single execution in Fig. 8. The diagram displays the numerical value of the distance to the target for a member of the swarm (vertical axis) over the number of iterations (horizontal axis). Five tags at different times are used to indicate different stages of the process, represented graphically by screenshots around the diagram and enlarged in Figure 11 for better visualization: initial random distribution of the robots in the scene, high value of fitness function (stage 1); advancing towards the target point but still no clear idea about where it is, fitness function decreasing steadily (stage 2); initial swarming around the current global best and approaching to (but still far from) the target, fitness function reaches a transient plateau (stage 3); arriving into in the neighborhood of the target point, fitness function already decreasing until new transient plateau again (stage 4); the swarm advances until achieving the target point, fitness function decreases until convergence (stage 5).

Figure 10: Convergence diagram for the execution in Figure 8.

6. Comparison with other alternative approaches

Regarding the design of swarm robotics based on bats, a very recent paper [30] introduced *Bat Bot*, an autonomous flying robot aimed at replicating the flight of real bats in a physical environment. Aerial robots based on insects and birds had already been described in the literature, but bats are particularly challenging because of their complex body skeleton (compared to birds and insects) and highly irregular flying patterns. The wings of *Bat Bot* are simplified versions of the original: instead of over 40 joints of the original bats, *Bat Bot* contains only nine joints (five of them controlled by mini-motors and four that are merely passive) made of lightweight carbon fibre, combined with an ultra-thin silicone membrane that mimics the bat skin covering each wing. As a result, the robot weighs only 93 grams and is controlled using tiny motors in its backbone. It also has onboard sensors to measure the angle of the joints for adjustment during the flight. This design brings significant improvements over current aerial robots in terms of energy efficiency due to their articulated soft wing architecture, and the fact that wing flexibility amplifies the motion of the robot's actuators. Complex movements involving asymmetric wing folding of the main flexible wings to control the heading of the robot are also possible. Furthermore, the *Bat Bot* does not use high-speed rotors, making it less noisy and intrusive than other flying robots. Note, however, that the design is exclusively focused on replicating the flying pattern of bats rather than on the collective behavior of bats as a swarm.

Figure 11: Individual pictures of the stage in the convergence diagram of Figure 10: (top) stage 1; (middle) stage 2; (bottom) stage 3.

Figure 11: (*cont'd*) Individual pictures of the stage in the convergence diagram of Figure 10: (top) stage 4; (bottom) stage 5.

7. Conclusions and Future Work

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- [1] Arkin, C.R.: Behavior-Based Robotics. MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass, USA (1998).
- [2] Arvin, F., Samsudin, K., Ramli, A. R.: Development of a miniature robot for swarm robotic application. *International Journal of Computer and Electrical Engineering*, **1**, 436–442 (2009).

- [3] F. Arvin, F., Murray, J.C., Shi, L., Zhang, C., Yue, S.: Development of an autonomous micro robot for swarm robotics. In: *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Mechatronics and Automation*, Tianjin, 635–640 (2014).
- [4] F. Arvin, Yue, S., Xiong, C.: Colias- Φ : an autonomous micro robot for artificial pheromone communication. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Robotics Research*, **4**(4), 349–353 (2015).
- [5] Blum, C., Merkle, D. (eds.): *Swarm Intelligence: Introduction and Applications*. Natural Computing Series. Springer Berlin Heidelberg (2008).
- [6] Bonabeau, E., Dorigo, M., Theraulaz, G.: *Swarm Intelligence: From Natural to Artificial System*. Oxford University Press, New York (1999).
- [7] Caprari, G., Estier, T., Siegwart, R.: Fascination of down scaling - Alice the sugar cube robot. *Journal of Micro-Mechatronics*, **1**(3), 177–189 (2002).
- [8] Caprari, G., Siegwart, R.: Mobile micro-robots ready to use: Alice. Proceedings of the IEEE IRS/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems –IROS 2005. Edmonton, Canada, 38453850 (2005).
- [9] Engelbrecht, A.P.: *Fundamentals of Computational Swarm Intelligence*. John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, England (2005).
- [10] Faigl, J., Krajník, T., Chudoba, J., Preucil, L., Saska, M.: Low-cost embedded system for relative localization in robotic swarms. In: *Proc. of IEEE Int. Conf. on Robotics and Automation - ICRA'2013*, pp. 993–998 (2013).
- [11] Gerkey, B.P. Vaughan, R.T., Howard, A.: The player/stage project: Tools for multi-robot and distributed sensor systems. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Robotics (Coimbra, Portugal)*, pp. 317–323 (2003).
- [12] Hassanien, A. E., Emary, E.: *Swarm Intelligence, Principles, Advances, and Applications*. CRC Press, Portland, USA (2015).
- [13] Iglesias, A., Gálvez, A.: Nature-inspired swarm intelligence for data fitting in reverse engineering: recent advances and future trends. *Studies in Computational Intelligence*, **637**, pp. 151–175 (2016).
- [14] Iglesias, A., Gálvez, A., Collantes, M.: Bat algorithm for curve parameterization in data fitting with polynomial Bézier curves. In: *Proc. of Cyberworlds 2015, Visby (Sweden)*, IEEE Computer Society Press, Los Alamitos, CA, pp. 107–114 (2015).
- [15] Iglesias, A., Gálvez, A., Collantes, M.: Global-support rational curve method for data approximation with bat algorithm. In: *Proc. of Int. Conference Artificial Intelligence and Applications - AIAI'2015, Bayonne (France)*. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology, **458** pp. 191–205 (2015).

- [16] Iglesias, A., Gálvez, A., Collantes, M.: A Bat algorithm for polynomial Bézier surface parameterization from clouds of irregularly sampled data points. In: Proc. of Int. Conference Natural Computation 2015 - ICNC'2015, Zhangjiajie (China). IEEE Computer Society Press, Los Alamitos CA, pp. 1034–1039 (2015).
- [17] Iglesias, A., Gálvez, A., Collantes, M.: Four adaptive memetic bat algorithm schemes for Bézier curve parameterization. Transactions on Computational Science XXVIII, LNCS 9590, pp. 127–145 (2016).
- [18] Jackson, J.: Microsoft robotics studio: a technical introduction. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine*, **14**(4) 82–87 (2007).
- [19] Kernbach, S., Thenius, R., Kernbach, O., Schmickl, T.: Re-embodiment of honey-bee aggregation behavior in an artificial micro-robotic system. *Adaptive Behavior*, **17**(3), 237–259 (2009).
- [20] Kennedy, J., Eberhart, R.C., Shi, Y.: Swarm Intelligence, Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, San Francisco (2001).
- [21] JMcLurkin, J.: Stupid robot tricks: a behavior-based distributed algorithm library for programming swarms of robots. M.S. thesis, *Massachusetts Institute of Technology* (2004).
- [22] McLurkin, J., Smith, J.: Distributed algorithms for dispersion in indoor environments using a swarm of autonomous mobile robots. In: *Distributed autonomous robotic systems*, **6**, Springer, 399–408 (2007)
- [23] McLurkin, J., Lynch, A. Rixner, S. Barr, T. Chou, A., Foster, K., Bilstein, S.: A low-cost multi-robot system for research, teaching, and outreach. in: *Distributed Autonomous Robotic Systems*, **83**, Springer, 597–609 (2013).
- [24] McLurkin, J., Smith, J. Frankel, J., Sotkowitz, D., Blau, D., Schmidt, B.: Speaking swarmish: Human-robot interface design for large swarms of autonomous mobile robots, in AAAI spring symposium, 72–75 (2006).
- [25] Michel, O.: Webots: professional mobile robot simulation. *Journal of Advanced Robotics Systems*, **1**(1) 39–42 (2004).
- [26] Mondada, F. Franzi, E., Guignard, A.: The development of Khepera. *Proceedings of the 1st International Khepera Workshop*, HNI-Verlagsschriftenreihe, Heinz Nixdorf Institut, **64**, 7–14 (1999).
- [27] Mondada, F., Gambardella, L.M., Floreano, D., Nolfi, S., Deneubourg, J.-L., Dorigo, M.: The cooperation of swarm-bots: physical interactions in collective robotics. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine*, **12**(2), 21–28 (2005).

- [28] Mondada, F., Bonani, M., Raemy, X., Pugh, J., Cianci, C., Klapotocz, A., Magnenat, S., Zufferey, J.C., Floreano, D., Martinoli, A.: The e-Puck, a robot designed for education in engineering. In: *Proceedings of the 9th conference on autonomous robot systems and competitions*, 1(1), 59–65 (2009).
- [29] Pugh, J., Raemy, X., Favre, C., Falconi, R., Martinoli, A.: A fast onboard relative positioning module for multirobot systems. *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, **14**(2), 151–162 (2009).
- [30] Ramezani, A., Chung, S.J., Hutchinson, S.: A biomimetic robotic platform to study flight specializations of bats. *Science Robotics*, **2**(3). Art. No. eaal2505, (2017).
- [31] Rubenstein, M., Ahler, C., Nagpal, R.: Kilobot: A low cost scalable robot system for collective behaviors. In: *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation – ICRA’2012*, 3293–3298 (2012).
- [32] Rubenstein, M., Cabrera, A., Werfel, J., Habibi, G., McLurkin, J., Nagpa, N.I.: Collective transport of complex objects by simple robots: theory and experiments. *International conference on Autonomous Agents and Multi-Agent Systems – AAMAS 2013*: 47–54 (2013).
- [33] Rubenstein, M., Ahler, C., Hoff, N., Cabrera, A., Nagpal, N.: Kilobot: A low cost robot with scalable operations designed for collective behaviors. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, **62**(7), 966–975 (2014)
- [34] Rubenstein, M., Cornejo, A., Nagpal, N.: Programmable self-assembly in a thousand-robot swarm. *Science*, **345**(6198), 795–799 (2014).
- [35] Gauci, M., Ortiz, M.E., Rubenstein, M., Nagpa, N.I.: Error Cascades in Collective Behavior: A Case Study of the Gradient Algorithm on 1000 Physical Agents. *International conference on Autonomous Agents and Multi-Agent Systems – AAMAS 2017*, 1404–1412 (2017).
- [36] Sahin, E.: Swarm robotics: from sources of inspiration to domains of application. In: *Swarm robotics, lecture notes in computer science, Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, **3342**, 10–20 (2005).
- [37] Sauter, J. A., Matthews, R., Parunak, H. V. D., Brueckner, S. A.: Effectiveness of digital pheromones controlling swarming vehicles in military scenarios. *Journal of Aerospace Computing, Information, and Communication*, **4**(5) (2007) 753–769.
- [38] Saska, M., Vonasek, V., Krajník, T., Preucil, L.: Coordination and navigation of heterogeneous MAVUGV formations localized by a hawk-eye-like approach under a model predictive control scheme. *International Journal of Robotics Research*, **33**(10) (2014) 1393–1412.

- [39] Schmickl, T., Thenius, R., Moeslinger, C., Radspieler, G., Kernbach, S., Szymanski, M., Crailsheim, K.: Get in touch: cooperative decision making based on robot-to-robot collisions. *Autonomous Agents and Multi-Agent Systems*, **18**(1), 133–155 (2009).
- [40] Seyfried, J., Szymanski, M., Bender, N., Estana, R., Thiel, M., Wörn, H.: The i-swarm project: intelligent small world autonomous robots for micro-manipulation. In: Swarm robotics. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, **3342**, 70–83 (2005).
- [41] Suarez, P., Iglesias, A.: Bat algorithm for coordinated exploration in swarm robotics. In: Del Ser, J. (ed.): Int. Conf. on Harmony Search Algorithm – ICHSA 2017. *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 514. Springer, Singapore 134–144 (2017).
- [42] Tan, Y., Zheng, Z.Y.: Research advance in swarm robotics. *Defence Technology Journal*, 9(1) (2013) 18–39.
- [43] Turgut A.E., Celikkanat, H., Gokce, F., Sahin E.: Self-Organized Flocking with a Mobile Robot Swarm. *Int. Conf. on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems – AAMAS 2008*, 39–46 (2008).
- [44] Turgut A.E., Celikkanat, H., Gokce, F., Sahin E.: Self-organized flocking in mobile robot swarms. *Swarm Intelligence*, **2**(2) 97–120 (2008).
- [45] Valdastri, P., Corradi, P., Menciassi, A., Schmickl, T., Crailsheim, K., Seyfried, J., Dario, P.: Micromanipulation, communication and swarm intelligence issues in a swarm microrobotic platform. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, **54**(10) 789–804 (2006).
- [46] Vasarhelyi, G., Virgh, C., Tarcai, N., Somorjai, G., Vicsek, T.: Outdoor flocking and formation flight with autonomous aerial robots. In: Proc. of IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems - IROS 2014, pp. 3866–3873 (2014).
- [47] Vaughan, R.: Massively multi-robot simulation in stage. *Swarm Intelligence*, **2**(2-4), 189–208 (2008).
- [48] Wagner, I., Bruckstein, A.: Special Issue on Ant Robotics. *Annals of Mathematics and Artificial Intelligence*, **31**(1-4) (2001).
- [49] Yang, X.-S.: *Nature-Inspired Metaheuristic Algorithms* (2nd. Edition). Luniver Press, Frome, UK (2010).
- [50] Yang, X.S.: A new metaheuristic bat-inspired algorithm. *Studies in Computational Intelligence*, Springer Berlin, 284, pp. 65–74 (2010).
- [51] Yang, X. S.: Bat algorithm for multiobjective optimization. *Int. J. Bio-Inspired Computation*, **3**(5) (2011), 267-274.

- [52] Yang, X.S., Gandomi, A.H.: Bat algorithm: a novel approach for global engineering optimization. *Engineering Computations*, **29**(5) (2012), 464–483.
- [53] Yang, X.S.: Bat algorithm: literature review and applications. *Int. J. Bio-Inspired Computation*, **5**(3) (2013), 141–149.
- [54] Yang, X.S.: *Nature-Inspired Optimization Algorithms*. Elsevier (2014).
- [55] Yang, X.S.: *Nature-Inspired Computation in Engineering*. *Studies in Computational Intelligence Series*, , Vol 637. Springer Switzerland (2016).
- [56] Zahugi, E.M.H., Shabani, A.M., Prasad, T.V.: Libot: Design of a low cost mobile robot for outdoor swarm robotics. In: *Proc. of IEEE International Conference on Cyber Technology in Automation, Control, and Intelligent Systems - CYBER'2012*, pp.342–347 (2012)